

Experiences of the Academic Achievers with Parental Involvement: A Transcendental Phenomenology Study

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Abstract

Research overwhelmingly showed that parental involvement in their children's learning positively affects child's academic performance. This study explored the experiences of academic achievers with parental involvement. A Transcendental Phenomenology design was employed since understanding human experiences from the perspective of the people who are living them. This method helps researchers uncover the essence of human experiences, shedding light on the underlying meanings and structures that shape our understanding of the world. It helps researchers explore the academic achievers' experiences with parental involvement. The results revealed majority answered having parental involvement in academic field motivates them to take education more seriously. It was further revealed that when parents are interacting with their children helps them to be more motivated to do schoolwork. This study provides critical information for parents, principals, teachers, and policy makers attempting to implement parents' involvement initiatives, as well as implications for further research.

Keywords: Parents involvement, Transcendental Phenomenology, Academic achievers

Introduction

Parental involvement in the learning activities of their children and the perceived impact of parents on their children's achievement are of continuing interest to educators as they are trying to find ways to improve the academic achievement of their students. In the last few decades, the importance of parental involvement in schools has increasingly gained recognition at both state and national levels. For example, the eighth goal of the National Education Goals, as set out in the Goals 2000: Educate America Act, noted that every school should promote a partnership between home and school that will increase parental involvement and participation in the social, emotional, and academic growth of children (U.S. Department of Education, 1994).

Numerous studies have been done to confirm the assumption that students do better when their parents are involved in their education (Bronfenbrenner, Karnes & Lee, Florin & Doke are cited by the State of Iowa Department of Education, 1998) "Henderson and Berla's study (as cited in Bowen, 1999 p. 1), stated, According to a review of 66 studies of how students succeed in school when parents become involved in children's

education at school and in the community, the results include one or more of the following: higher grades and test scores, better attendance and regularly completed assignments, fewer placements in special education and remedial classes, more positive attitudes and behavior in school, higher graduation rates, and greater enrollment in secondary education.

Bempechant (1990) noted that accumulated evidence supports the importance of parent involvement in children's education. Some parents have the skills to foster academic achievement. Most importantly, research shows that when teachers and educational administrators are strongly committed to involving parents in their children's education, academic outcomes for children can be very positive.

Schools must adhere to the integrated support system for their students. You must develop a productive relationship with parents and encourage shared responsibility for students' academic achievement in the system. In this approach, the efforts of parents to support schools are encouraged, and parental involvement is increased, and they are directly contributing to an effective educational framework.

According to (Sheldon, 2017) the study shows a significant positive relationship between parental involvement in education and students' academic performance. It is recommended from the study that parents should play a leading role in supporting their children's education since they are the first to expose children to the social and academic world.

This study was related to Tuyom Senior High School at Tuyom, Carcar City, Cebu. The focus of this study is to explore the experiences of academic achievers alongside with their parents. The chosen participants can only those academic achievers on the grade 12 students of Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS). Their grades in the first semester will be the basis of this are included in the academic achievers list. This will also show how their parents affects their productiveness in school.

Literature Review

According to (Levitt & Dubner, 2005), Parenting, as an art and science, has a number of attractive characteristics to an economist like Steve Levitt, who sees economics as a discipline with excellent tools for gaining answers but a serious shortage of interesting questions. People spend huge amounts of time and money seeking for advice on parenting, as reflected by the blooming media industry devoted to the subject. Today, parenting theories are gaining influence into shaping childhood and education policies. Still, much of what is believed in this field rests on experts' opinions, and there is few solid evidence on the benefits of parental investments.

The Effects of Parental Involvement on Student Achievement

Many researchers have examined the relationship between parental involvement and student's academic achievement. There are many variables that have influenced the relationship, such as, the impact of family communication, single-parent families, cultural differences, and parental expectations. Current research supports the fact that student's benefit the most when their parents are involved in their lives (Pomerantz and Dong, 2006).

By having researched this topic it is clear that the way parents communicate both verbally and nonverbally can greatly affect their child's achievement (Pomerantz, Wang, & Ng, 2005). Children are smart at reading cues and can easily pick up on how their parents perceive their competence. Later, this paper will go into detail on how parent's attitudes and perceived competence can impact their child's academic achievement.

Another factor that has been examined is the influence of single-parent families. It seems as though being a child raised in a single-parent family can be especially difficult if the non-resident parent is not involved in their lives (Howard, Burke, Borkowski, & Whitman, 2006). According to Howard et al., (2006), there are many other variables that can affect student achievement including mothers' education level, job stability, and the amount time the resident parent spends with their child. Specifics on single-parent families will be discussed later in this paper.

There is evidence that supports cultural differences play a role in the effects of parental involvement on student achievement. In a country of many cultures, it is not surprising that culture can have an influence on student achievement. Often, the communication barrier has impacted many students in the United States (Castillo, Conoley, & Brossart, 2004). Students typically speak their native language at home and then speak English in school. This alone puts students of a different culture at a disadvantage.

Researchers have looked at the effects of parental expectations, as well (Luthar, Shoum, & Brown, 2006). Often times, parents have too high of expectations. This can lead to students being overloaded with extracurricular activities and the feeling like that they never measure up. It is important to have high expectations as a parent, but to be realistic in what their child can handle. Each child is different in what they can handle, so it is crucial that parents look at each one of their children individually.

Many parents are unaware of the impact they can have on their children. Parents have a huge responsibility in communicating and supporting their child throughout their academic career. Unfortunately, there are situations that do not allow parents to fully communicate and support their child. This paper touches on those scenarios and allows readers to better understand the relationship between parental involvement and student achievement. It is especially important for school counselors to be aware of the factors that influence their students' academic achievement. By knowing these factors, counselors can be prepared for appropriate techniques and interventions for both students and parents.

According to Gould, (1999), "The research all shows, they say, that children do better in school when their parents are involved. Parent involvement can be divided into two general categories: school-site involvement and home involvement (Zellman & Waterman, 1998). They focused on five measures of parent-school involvement: attendance at school events, participation on a school council or advisory committee, regular volunteer activities, employment at school, and PTA meetings. Gestwicki (1996) added parents as learners to this list, and indicated that home involvement includes helping the child with homework, communicating with the child about school, and spending "quality" time with the child.

Parental involvement is not a new concept but has evolved, in this country, from parents being concerned about their son's education and their daughter's dowry to a genuine concern for the education of both sons and daughters. According to Gould, (2018), The research all shows, they say, that children do better in school when their parents are involved.

According to (Barge & Loges, 2017) Parental involvement is a key predictor of a student's academic success. However, little research has explored whether parent, student, and teacher perceptions are similar regarding what constitutes parental involvement and the communication activities it entails.

Added by, Benson, Mudrey-Camino and Steineret (2010), parental involvement in assignment can be a means to keep parents well-informed of the child's strengths and weaknesses in several subject areas, mainly reading. A study by Cai (2003) illustrated that participation parents is a statistically weighty forecaster of their child's level of achievement in Maths and promoted positive behaviour and emotional development. Domitrovich, and Welsh (2004) showed that parents' involvement in their children's reading activities at home had a significant influence, not only on their reading ability, language comprehension and expressive language skills, but also on their interest in reading. Children who worked with their parents at home on Math assignment achieved better Math grades (Bartel, 2010). It demonstrated that when parents are involved in a child's schooling by assisting them with homework, communicating with teachers and attending all events at school, it helps the child to do very well in the all the subjects the school.

According to Kohl, Lengua and McMahon (2000), children attend school regularly, act better, perform well academically from kindergarten through high school, go farther in school when parents more are involved in their schoolwork. Similarly, Barnard (2004), found that academic performance of students profoundly depends upon the parental involvement in their academic activities to attain a higher level of quality in academic success. Since parents are the first teachers of their children, they need to take a leading role in their children's education. Parent involvement in a child's education is a key issue ensuring students' success, growth and development in life. Students will take education more seriously, do well academically, display better behaviour in school and assume greater responsibility for his or her actions when they found their parents are actively involved.

The Effects of without Parental Involvement

Teacher training is relevant because significant emphasis is placed on the importance of parental involvement for both learner outcomes and the life of the schools that their children attend (Epstein, 1995, 2018; Mansfield-Barry & Stwayi, 2017). Epstein (2018) notes that very few teacher while starting their profession have knowledge of what they need to do to initiate and implement partnership programs that will inform and involve parents in a way that will keep them active in their children's education during the entire academic year.

That said, parental involvement should not be construed as only pertaining to financial involvement (albeit that monetary contributions are important): parents ought to be directly involved in the academic, social and emotional needs of their children. As such, parents from poor backgrounds have different ways of participating in learner education (Anderson & Minke, 2007).

Shearer (2006) argues that parental non-involvement is exacerbated by an overarching worldwide phenomenon, whereby schools are unable to clearly delineate parental roles from those of the school, thus introducing conflict where there ought to be collaboration. Therefore, the inability of parents in impoverished communities to enhance learners' learning abilities positively is aggravated by the failure of schools to selectively cooperate with these stakeholders (Singh, Mbokodi & Msila, 2004; Van Loggenberg, 2013). Parental involvement thus needs to extend beyond theorization – especially at home, where educational inequality is deemed to originate (Harris & Robinson, 2016).

Furthermore, schools are seemingly not initiating or/and implementing appropriate strategies that are genuinely inclusive, welcoming or encouraging, and are thereby preventing parents from volunteering on a regular basis (Msila, 2012; Van Loggenberg, 2013). Smith (2006) and Msila (2012) argue that schools can overcome parental disengagement by following robust, inclusive approaches with the capacity to unlock parents' existing potentials and enhance their meaningful participation (Park & Holloway, 2017). Therefore, the need to empower teachers with family and community involvement skills to enable them have the capacity to identify the potentials of parents and exploit them for the benefit of the learners and the schools is becoming more relevant (Epstein, 2018).

Broader social contexts also impede the establishment of strong relationships between parents and schools, with the former often feeling excluded (Walker & Berthelsen, 2010). Parents thus become increasingly disconnected from what they ought to be doing, and may be alienated from gaining knowledge that could spur them to get involved (in diverse school programs relating to their children's education) (Van Loggenberg, 2013). For Donkor (2010) there is a concomitant non-negotiable, urgent need to change parents' perceptions of education and improve their participation.

Clearly, parents – irrespective of context – can only help to guarantee a positive educational future for their children by working hand-in-glove with schools (Msila, 2012). Since educators are also likely to reap the benefits of parental involvement in the form of improved teaching and learning, they need to spearhead engagements that are aimed at enhancing such participation (Jacobs, 2008). Undoubtedly, when parents and educators come together and work holistically towards learners' education, by focusing on the academic, social and emotional needs of the latter, success is bound to happen naturally (Epstein, 1995; Epstein, 2018) – this, while recognizing all children's rights to quality basic education (Manseld-Barry & Stwayi, 2017).

Significance of Parental Involvement

Teachers can have a better understanding of infants by implementing parental involvement because infants spend much more time with their parents than any other people. Parents are infants' first teacher and continue to play an active role in their education and lives. According to the study conducted by Bronfenbrenner (2017), students' achievement was always shaped by their life outside the school and highlighted the importance of parents' role.

The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) and many other studies show that students show a better ability to read when their parents are involved in their education and when the parents themselves value reading. According to the PISA, certain activities are more strongly related to better student performance than others. For example, reading books to children when they are just beginning primary school benefits children because it shows them that reading is something that their parents value. Children of parents who are involved in their education in these ways are generally found to be more receptive in their studies and individual projects. It should also come as no surprise that

parents who read to their children, have books available, take trips, guide TV watching, and provide stimulating experiences which contribute to student achievement.

Involving parents in their children's literacy activities not only benefits their children but also parents themselves. Numerous benefits have been reported for the parents, including greater skill acquisition, greater confidence and self-esteem, a better child-parent relationship and increased engagement with learning (Cited in Bonci, A. 2011).

Furthermore, parents who maintain frequent contact with the school have higher achieving children than parents who have infrequent contact. In turn, schools that are well connected with the community tend to have higher achieving students than schools with fewer ties. Parents who become involved in their children's schooling tend also to develop positive attitudes towards their children's teachers. They rate teachers higher in interpersonal and teaching skills, perceive them as wanting them to develop their children and as very helpful in suggesting ideas for home activities (Epstein, 1987). Parents' degree of involvement is also likely to be affected by the school itself. If teachers care about the welfare of the child, show respect, and trust for parents, and develop communication ties with families, parents are more willing to become actively involved in their children's schooling (Hoover-Dempsey & Sandler, 1997). Therefore, to increase parental involvement, schools need to provide a welcoming climate where the school staff is respectful and responsive to parents (Wherry, 2009).

Involved parents tend also to enlist the support of others, become actively involved in community issues, and further their education (Becher, in Hemderson, 1987). Children whose parents are involved in these ways are generally found to be more receptive to language, show a better ability to read and learn when their parents are involved in their education and when the parents themselves value reading. Additionally, children of involved parents are motivated to learn for learning's sake and have more control over their academic performance because they adopt their parents' positive attitudes towards school and learning. They know, too, that they can obtain guidance from their parents on how to navigate school and its challenges. Remember that children learn more by imitating their significant adults.

Desforges and Aboucher (2003), however, found that parent-child conversations in the home were more valuable, in terms of encouraging children's school achievement than parents' involvement in school activities. In other words, schools should encourage parents to talk to their children about school activities at home. This suggests that parent-child conversations at home about school activities are directly linked to parental involvement. For example, if teachers assign homework, parents who are actively involved in their children's education are undoubtedly encouraged to talk about the homework and offer help where possible.

After adjusting for child, parent, and household factors, the study aimed to investigate the relationship between parental motivating beliefs, parental perceptions of invitations for involvement, parental perceived life context, and parental at-home and at-school involvement. The study's findings show that parental involvement at home and at school is substantially correlated with the kid's grade level, parental sense of self-efficacy, and invitations from the child for involvement. Parental participation at school was also substantially correlated with time and energy. Considering the significance of parental participation as a protection for kids' mental health, the article concludes with recommendations for school-based mental health treatments based on the research. The results specifically address how to incorporate family participation programs and boost parental involvement while accounting for the reasons why parents want to get involved in an international context (Reininger, T., 2014)

According to Sebastian, Moon, and Cunningham, (2017), three characteristics of parental participation with schools were identified by factor analysis of the responses from both principals and parents: parent volunteerism, parent-initiated involvement, and teacher-initiated involvement. Student success gaps between schools were favorably predicted by principal reports of parent-initiated involvement. Parent reports of teacher-initiated involvement in schools were a poor predictor of student achievement. The study highlights how crucial it is to comprehend the information source for survey metrics. PISA study parent surveys provide information on parental participation that can be used to describe student success variation within a school, while principal reports can be used to forecast variation between schools. School grades served as an indicator for academic success.

The findings show that there is no substantial connection between home-family participation and academic achievement, with the exception of two of the criteria taken into account. The work of parents and the availability of resources for informal education are these two elements. A greater connection exists between family participation and a child's access to informal education resources and academic success. Students who have working parents do better academically than those who don't. The findings indicate that girls outperform males in school and receive greater family attention, even though gender does not seem to have a substantial impact on these outcomes (Tárraga, García, & Reyes, 2017).

According to Wilder, (2014), regardless of how parental engagement is defined or how accomplishment is measured, the data showed that there is a positive association between parental involvement and academic achievement. Additionally, the results showed that this association was highest if parental expectations for their children's academic success were classified as parental participation. However, if parental involvement was limited to helping with schoolwork, the effect of parental involvement on students' academic progress was least significant. Lastly, it was shown that there was a constant correlation between parental participation and academic achievement in all grade levels and ethnic groupings. But depending on the kind of test used to gauge student performance, that relationship's strength changed.

In a study, Pena (2000) found that parents' school involvement positively correlates school environment and classroom learning. Shumow et al. (2004) concluded that parents' involvement in school was positively related to how skilled students feel during class, their grade attainment, and long-term academic expectations. Parental expectation has appeared as a variable in many parental involvement studies carried by researchers of different parts of the world and generally the found that there is a strong relationship with students' academic achievements.

The study's findings showed that parental participation is essential for ensuring that kids fully succeed in school possible in terms of both conduct and academics. According to the findings, there are several reasons why parental involvement in the classroom and at home should be encouraged. These include the following: (1) it gives kids a positive message about the value of education; (2) it keeps parents updated on their child's progress; and (3) it enables the school to achieve more. The research invitation letter, the questionnaire, the questionnaire findings, and the interview questions are all located in the appendices (Akimoff, K. G., 2017).

Research Methods

This study is qualitative in nature and utilized Transcendental phenomenology survey research methods in exploring the experiences of the academic achievers with parental involvement. Furthermore, this study used a transcendental phenomenology design. Transcendental phenomenology examines the experienced that transcends the structure of awareness to learn about its underlying structures. This method helps researchers uncover the essence of human experiences, shedding light on the underlying meanings and structures that shape our understanding of the world.

The use of a transcendental phenomenological approach to qualitative research was the appropriate choice for the design of this study because the phenomenon studied focused on the common meaning of the lived experiences (Creswell, 2013) of a group of elementary teachers assisting struggling readers during the COVID-19 pandemic. Using a qualitative design allowed the researcher to use inductive and emerging procedures shaped by the collection and the analysis of the data, whereas a phenomenological approach allowed for a fuller description of “what” was experienced and “how” the participants experienced it (Creswell, 2013).

Results and Discussion

Parental Involvement

Table 1
Impact Of Parental Involvement in Academic Performance

Responses in Verbatim	Formulated Meaning	Emergent Themes
R2: When my parents help me with my schoolwork’s, they make me better in school. It makes me take education more seriously, do well academically, display better behavior in my school and assume greater responsibility for my actions.	Respondent 2 said that the impact of parental involvement to her is it made her do better in school. said that the impact of parental involvement in academic performance is to take education more seriously and display a good behavior.	
R3: it makes me motivated to study and work hard. It lets me communicate with them if I’m having trouble and difficulties about my study.	The respondent 3 said that the impact of parental involvement to her is it made her more motivated and to work hard. said that the impact of parental involvement in academic performance is to take education more seriously and display a good behavior.	
R16: for me it has a great impact as a student. If parents are actively involved in the academic performance of his/her child, the student will take education more seriously, display better behavior, and will do well in his/her studies.no impact because I have my own thing to do whatever I want.	Respondent 16 said that the impact of parental involvement in academic performance is to take education more seriously and display a good behavior.	Take education more seriously

R6: there are lots of impact when it comes to my performance mainly high grades and my parents contribute to my emotional stability as well as resilience. I think it's a great impact for me because parental involvement is important as a student because it can motivate me to study and strive harder.

Respondents 15 said that the impact of having parental involvement have a lot of impact to her because it contributes it to her emotional stability.

Communication

R7: it gives happiness when your parents know to communicate of how your academic performance is.

Respondent 7 said that it gives her joy knowing that her parents are communicating with her about her academic performance.

R8: the biggest impact of parental involvement as a grade 12 student, is that I can boost my academic performance in any subject that I am taking with, moreover, it makes me more comfortable in doing some task or work given. I am immensely grateful to have my mom that always checking up on me of what my problems in school I am facing.

Respondent 8 said that the impact of parental involvement in herself is she is happy to have someone to check upon her about herself and about academic.

R9: I guess for me, the impact of it is I can achieve higher grades, scores, or overall academic achievements, because they can provide mental support to me and motivation.

Respondent 9 said that the impact of parental involvement to her is she have a high grade because parents help her motivates.

Motivation

R10: the impact of parental involvement in my academic performance is it can boost my confidence; it motivates me to succeed academically.

Respondent 10 said that the impact of parental involvement is It helps her to boost her confidence and motivates her.

R11: they motivate us to continue schooling and they provide us anything.

Respondent 11 said that the impact of parental involvement is it help them to be motivated.

R12: the impact of parental involvement in my academic performance is they motivate me to continue what I've started; they are also my good role model.

Respondent 12 said that the impact of parental involvement to her is she have a high grade because parents help her motivates.

R15: I think it's a great impact for me because parental involvement is important as a student because it can motivate me to study and strive harder.

Respondent 6 said that the impact of parental involvement in his academic performance is big because it made him motivated.

R4: I think it's a great impact for me because parental involvement is important as a student because it can motivate me to study and strive harder.

Respondent 17 said that the impact of parental involvement in his academic performance is big because it made him motivated.

The table 1 shows the responses about the impact of the having parental involvement if their academic performances. Out of the total respondents, four indicated that the impact of parental involvement can help them to take education more seriously, seven responded that it is their motivation and only 1 stated that there is no impact. Therefore, many of the responses about the impact of having parental serves as a motivation to do better in school and take education more seriously.

Effectiveness of having Parental Involvement

Table 2
Effectiveness of having Parental Involvement in Academic Performance

Responses in Verbatim	Formulated Meaning	Emergent Themes
R1: For me, it is very effective because my parents always motivate me and inspired me so that I will think positively and wanted to go to school every day.	Respondent 1 said that parental involvement is effective because his parents are the one who motivates them to do good in school.	
R10: as an academic achiever, it helps me to study more, it creates a supportive environment that foster success.	Respondent 10 said that parental involvement is effective for her as an academic achiever because it helps her to study more.	Motivation
R5: it is very effective because their involvement can help me motivated to achieve my goals.	Respondent 5 said that parental involvement is effective because his parents are the one who motivates them to achieve their goals.	
R6: it is effective in a way that their support can have a significant or a positive effect for me. As an academic achiever, my parents are the reason why I'm an honor.	Respondent 6 that parental involvement is effective because her parents are the one who made her in the honor list.	
R9: I had the courage to do more and tend to perform better academically.	Respondent 9 said that parental involvement is effective because it can help her to perform better in school.	

R15: it helps me to improve myself and maintain a good grades.	Respondent 15 said that the effect of having parental involvement help her to have a high grade.	
R11: it is important to me since I am still dependent on them.	Respondent 11 said that parental involvement is important to her because she is still dependent to her parents.	
R12: it is important to me since I am still dependent on them	Respondent 12 said that parental involvement is important to her because she is still dependent to her parents	Dependent
R13: it is effective for me for having a parental involvement because they provide us with our need's every time we have school payments.	Respondent 13 said that the effect of parental involvement is it gives her confidence and stable mind.	
R3: It's very effective because they help me financially	Respondent 3 said that parental involvement is effective because it can help her financially	
R7: it is good, it gives you confidence and a stable mind	Respondent 7 said that the effect of parental involvement is it gives her confidence and stable mind.	Stable Mental Health
R16: it is good, it gives you confidence and a stable mind.	Respondent 16 said that the effect of parental involvement is it gives her confidence and stable mind.	

The table 2 presents the responses of the respondents about how effective parental involvement having is. Out of the total respondents, three of them said that it is effective because it gives them assurance to have a stable mental health, two responded that it is effective because they are still dependent in their parents, and the rest answered it is effective because it gives them motivation.

Effects of having Without Parental Involvement

Table 3

Responses in verbatim	Formulated Meaning	Emergent Themes
R1: It positively influences children's behavior. It can help students get a high grade because they see their parents as their inspiration.	Respondent 1 said that the effect of having parental involvement can helps students have a good grade.	
R2: It makes me feel supported and motivated to do better.	Respondent 2 said that the effect of having parental involvement is it made them feel supported and motivated to do better.	

R4: it gives me a positive mindset and support.	Respondent 4 said that the effect of having parental involvement can give her a positive mind and support.	
R6: the effect of parental involvement to me it helps me more motivated.	Respondent 6 said that the effect of parental involvement can motivates her.	
R8: in my own personal experience, having parental involvement is kind a pleasure as an academic achiever since as far as I know, there's a lot of students that seek help on their parents. So, having this is helping me more motivated as a graduating student.	Respondent 8 said that with parental involvement can help her more motivated and it is a pleasure for her that her parents are involving in her academic performance.	Motivation to gain good grades
R9: be academically success, I can improve my behavior with the help of my parents, enhanced self-esteem, better mental health and healthy relationships.	Respondent 9 said that having parental involvement can help her have a good relationship with others, do better in school and have a healthy mental health.	
R12: it helps me motivated	Respondent 12 said that the effect of parental involvement can motivates her.	
R14: for me the effects of having parental involvement are that it improves students' attendance, social skills, and their behavior.	Respondent 14 said that the effect of having parental involvement can helps students have a good grade.	
R15: the effect of parental involvement to me it helps me more motivated.	Respondent 15 said that the effect of parental involvement can motivates her.	
R17: It makes me feel supported and motivated to do better.	Respondent 17 said that the effect of having parental involvement is it made them feel supported and motivated to do better.	

The table 3 showed the responses of the respondents about the effect of having parental involvement. All the respondents responded that having parental involvement can motivates them to do better in school, good character and they felt supported by their parents.

Table 4
Effects of without having parental involvement

Responses in Verbatim	Formulated Meaning	Emergent Themes
R1: Without parental involvement can have a problem behaviors and students can get low grades.	Respondent 1 said that without parental involvement will make students get bad grades.	
R4: sometimes it's good but my parents said that practice being an independent.	Respondent 4 stated that without parental involvement makes her feel less motivated.	
R6: I believe there are many effects but being not interest in going to school is the most common effect of it and to have vices and addiction to any things.	Respondent 6 says that the most common of without parental involvement can make their child not wanted to go to school and have possibility to be addicted to some illegal things.	

R7: it gives bad influence on the student having less parental involvement. In that case students may rebellious.

Respondent 7 said that without parental involvement can lead to students into a bad life and became rebellious.

Bad grades, less motivated and can lead to an addiction problem

R8: in my own perspective, I think the possible effects for having without a parental involvement is that there's a chance that your son/daughter wouldn't be at her/his good condition. Because we all know that there's so many issues in this generation and the main cause is depression so important to check/consult your children with their academic problems.

Respondent 8 said that without parental involvement can lead to a bad condition since this generation is prone for depression so, better to check their children about academic problems.

R10: effects of without parental involvement, it might lead to the students face negative effects on their academic performance, such as lack of motivation, opportunities to support and so on.

Respondent 10 said that without parental involvement can make the student less motivated.

R13: the effects of without parental involvement is that you can't think to overcome those opportunities just because you don't have any support with them.

Respondent 13 said that without parental involvement can make the student less motivated because of lack of support.

R14: it may lead student to have low self-assessment on their behavior since they don't monitor their child.

Respondent 14 said that without parental involvement will make students get bad grades.

R15: no support

Respondent 15 said that without parental involvement is basically no support parents.

R16: students might feel less motivated because their parents don't be involved in their academics

Respondent 16 said that without parental involvement can make the student less motivated.

R17: I feel less motivated, and it really affects my academic performance.

Respondent 17 stated that without parental involvement can make her feel less motivated and can get lower grades.

The table 4 presents effects without parental involvement in academic field. Majority of the respondents answered that without parental involvement, they are less motivated, they will have bad grades, have bad characteristics and behavior, and it can lead to a big problem such as joining or using illegal drugs.

Importance of Parental Involvement

Table 5
Importance of parental involvement

Responses in Verbatim	Formulated Meaning	Emergent Themes
R1: Parental involvement is very important because it helps students improves their attendance, social skills, and behavior.	Respondent 1 stated that parental involvement is important since it helps students improves attendance, social skills, and behavior.	
R3: very important because they help me in my academics.	Respondent 3 that parental involvement is important because it helps them have a good academic performance.	
R4: its important sometimes because they can give me strength.	Respondent 4 stated that parental involvement is effective because it can give get strength.	

R6: it is important because it motivate and give me a reason to become better because at the end of the day, I will work harder for them to be proud.

Respondent 6 said that parental involvement is important because it helps her become better in school.

R8: the parental involvement for me is essential for my daily life as a student since it would help my career worth risking for. Having that parental involvement is such an honor specifically I am now a graduating student.

Respondent 8 said that parental involvement is very essential for her since it will help her with her future career especially, she is currently a graduating student.

Motivation to do better in school

R9: it is very important because it can help their child study more or their children would feel that they were important to his/her family.

Respondent 9 said that parental involvement is important because it can help their child to be motivated to study hard.

R10: parental involvement is very important for me as an academic achiever because every time they are checking up on me, I felt motivated to achieve my goals.

Respondent 10 said that parental involvement is important because it can help their child to be motivated to study hard and achieve their goals.

R12: it can motivate me to continue what I've started.

Respondent 12 said that parental involvement is important because it can help their child to be motivated to study hard.

R14: the more parental involvement, the more I likely to become productive, motivated, and excel in academics.

Respondent 14 said that parental involvement is important because it can help students to become more productive and excel in academics.

R17: it is important because if parental is bad then students' attitude and characteristic will reflect to.

Respondent 17 said parental involvement is important because if there is no parental involvement or bad parental involvement the characteristics of the student will reflect.

The table 5 presents the importance of having parental involvement in your academic performance. All respondents said that having parental is significant especially to them a grade 12 students which is a graduating student. It helps them to feel motivated, take education more seriously and do better in school.

Table 6

Responses in Verbatim	Formulated Meaning	Emergent Themes
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R1: I will encourage them to involve in their child's academic performance because if not their child may struggle with their schoolwork's and feel disengaged or disconnected from their education, which can make them more likely to drop out.

Respondent 1 said that they will encourage parents to involve more to their child or else their child will struggle, feel disengaged and more likely to drop out.

R2: they should check their children and make them feel like they are worthy. Support them with the things they like.

Respondent 2 stated that they should tell the parents to check their children to make them like they are worthy, and they should support their children with the things they like to do.

R3: I can say that it's very sad that they didn't want their child to succeed in their academics.

Respondent 3 stated that it is very sad that parents don't have parental involvement.

R5: I can say that they don't want their students to excel in the academic field.

Respondent 5 said that if parents don't involve in their students' academic then they don't want their students to excel in academic field.

Encouragement to be involved in students' academic performance.

R6: I can say that maybe they are giving their give some privacy for their child's peace of mind. Also, it could be that parents are confident to their child is working hard at school.

Responses 6 still wore a face mask even when it's not mandatory, respondent 6 said that maybe parents didn't involve in their child is because parents are confident that their child is working hard in the school.

R8: all I can say is that they must consult their child for them to ensure that their child is in good terms because helping your child can make them more motivated and there's a possibility that their child would have a great future ahead.

Respondent 8 is encouraging parents to involve in their child academic performance so that it will ensure their child's future.

R9: all I can say is that their children might quit studying or have a low grade because parents have big impact to their child for them to motivate.

Respondent 9 said parents should involve because it might cause something bad like their child can get low grades and less motivated.

R10: parents who are not involved with their child's academic performance may be missing out an important opportunity to support and guide their child education.

Respondent 10 said that parents without involvement to their students' academic performance might be missing out an important opportunity.

R14: nowadays, I have observed that there are some parents who are not bothered about their child's academic performance. All I can say is that they should be aware and involve their selves about the performance of their child.

Respondent 14 said that parents must involve in their student's academic performance.

R15: they should know that their good advice is very important to the mind of their children.

Respondent 15 said that parents should know that their good advice matters to their child so they must involve in their child's academic.

The table 6 showed the opinions the respondents wanted to tell the parents who are not involving in their students' academic performance. All the respondents answered that they will encourage parents to involve in academic performance of their children because their students need their parents' involvement especially when students are having questions or any problems in school.

Conclusion

In conclusion, parental involvement has been a big factor on the student's academic performance. Students more likely to excel in school when their parents are motivating them to go on studying. Parental involvement isn't just about motivating their child, attending parent-teacher assembly, the sacrifices that they've made but its all about how can the joy and the experience that their child gained through their guidance. According to Wilder, S. (2014), regardless of how parental engagement is defined or how accomplishment is measured, the data showed that there is a positive association between parental involvement and academic achievement. Additionally, the results showed that this association was highest if parental expectations for their children's academic success were classified as parental participation. However, if parental involvement was limited to helping with schoolwork, the effect of parental involvement on students' academic progress was least significant. Lastly, it was shown that there was a constant correlation between parental participation and academic achievement in all grade levels and ethnic groupings. But depending on the kind of test used to gauge student performance, that relationship's strength changed.

Recommendations

Teachers and administrators of the school need to change their approach and attitude in dealing with parents, so parents we feel welcome and comfortable to involved school.

PTA meetings should be organized continuously through the year to help parents remain involved in the school and aware of weaknesses and strengths of the children.

The school should organize Parent-Teacher professional development to reinforce their partnership which will help them work together as a team.

Educators, school administrators and policy makers should design programs which enable parent involvement in child education at school and home.

It is important for parents to be aware on the necessity to visit their children in school. This habit helps parents to observe their children's progress more closely, getting a clear understanding of the children's academic development issues and creating a comfortable interaction with teachers and school staff.

Parents possess a key role and they should play this role to guide and back their children's developments and academic learnings because parents are the foremost teachers and the first educators which introduce the children to the society and school.

The schools' administrators should to take necessary steps to encourage parents in participating to enhance their children's academic outcomes and developing their skills in reading and numeracy at an early age.

Future research must emphasis on the impact of parental active involvement or association in children's education and how it might be related to socio-economic status and marital status. It should also compare parents' involvement in private and public schools with a larger sample. This could be achieved by conducting a quantitative study.

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